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The article analyzes the role of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies in optimizing business processes. The impact of AI on key business areas such as marketing, supply chain management, recruitment, financial and production processes is being investigated. The main advantages of using AI are explored, including increased efficiency, reduced costs and improved analytical capabilities. It is emphasized that, despite the significant advantages, the introduction of AI is associated with a number of challenges, such as high costs, the need for qualified personnel and risks associated with data security.

Keywords: artificial intelligence (AI), business processes, automation, business efficiency, machine learning (ML).

Introduction

Incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) technologies into business processes has become a critical area of focus for modern organizations seeking to improve efficiency and competitiveness. It is having a significant impact on various aspects of business by automating routine operations, improving data analysis, and supporting more informed decision-making.

Technologies in AI cover a wide range of areas, including machine learning (ML), big data analytics, natural language processing, and computer vision, opening up new opportunities for companies to improve internal processes and customer interactions. It is becoming an integral part of digital transformation and is helping to create new business models, improve productivity and better adapt to rapidly changing market conditions. However, AI adoption comes with a number of challenges, such as infrastructure costs and the need for specialized staff, and potential risks related to ethics and data security.

This article aims to analyze the theoretical foundations of AI implementation in business processes, assess the advantages and limitations of AI technologies, and determine the prospects for further development

and application of these technologies in the business environment.

Main part. Theoretical foundations and classification of AI technologies in business

Encompassing a wide range of tools, AI technologies facilitate process automation and support more informed business decision-making. AI is defined as a set of algorithms and systems capable of simulating human intellectual functions such as learning, perception, and analysis. The foundations of AI lie in fields such as ML, deep learning, big data analysis, natural language processing, and computer vision, each contributing essential methods and techniques that enable AI systems to learn, interpret data, and make autonomous decisions [1].

The 2023 Oxford Insights analysis assessed the readiness of national governments to implement and consider 39 indicators across 10 areas, covering three key aspects: government, technology sector, data, and infrastructure. The USA is on the 1st place of the rating, while significantly ahead of other countries in the «Technology Sector» category, scoring 12 points more than any other country. Kazakhstan is ranked 72 out of 188 with a final score of 48,56 (table 1).

Table 1.

Country ranking by AI readiness index

Indicator, country	Government	Technology sector	Data and infrastructure	Final score	Place
USA	86,04	81,02	87,32	84,80	1
Singapore	90,40	66,19	89,32	81,97	2
Great Britain	82,50	68,80	84,42	78,57	3
Finland	88,34	60,36	83,39	77,37	4
Canada	85,30	64,73	81,17	77,07	5
Kazakhstan	48,56	30,97	66,13	48,56	72

Unlike the USA, where the technology sector is a driving force of economic growth and innovation, the technology sector in Kazakhstan is identified as underdeveloped. This disparity reflects significant differences in infrastructure, investment levels, and policy priorities between the two countries. While the USA benefits from a mature ecosystem of tech companies,

research institutions, and venture capital, Kazakhstan faces challenges such as limited access to cutting-edge technologies, insufficient funding for innovation, and a lack of highly skilled professionals, which hinder the sector's growth and its contribution to the national economy (fig.1).

Figure 1. USA and Kazakhstan comparison [2]

The United States is actively advancing AI initiatives. Under the guidance of the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), government agencies are expanding AI standards aligned with the AI risk management framework. Similarly, Kazakhstan possesses considerable potential in AI but faces significant challenges, including limited educational resources. Although Kazakhstan is actively constructing AI infrastructure, such as information and IT centers, access to computing resources remains restricted, slowing AI development. Additional challenges include a lack of strategic vision, limited technological maturity, low innovation capacity, human capital shortages, and the need for legislative frameworks to address legal considerations and data protection in AI. To enhance its AI development index, Kazakhstan has adopted the «Concept for the Development of AI for 2024-2029» [3].

The introduction of AI technologies can lead to **cost savings and increase business efficiency**. The advantages of implementing AI in business include improved process efficiency, optimized resource use, enhanced service quality, and increased customer satisfaction. For example, AI allows businesses to automate data analysis, accelerating decision-making and reducing human error. Automating tasks such as inventory management, ad analysis, and recruitment can save time on routine operations. AI-based chatbots can automate customer interactions and reduce labor costs. AI can help with budgeting, cost tracking, and risk assessment. In addition, investment strategies and portfolio management can be optimized using it.

However, adopting AI also presents **challenges**. High implementation costs are one of the primary obstacles; building AI infrastructure – including advanced computing capabilities, data storage, and complex algorithms – demands substantial financial resources. Furthermore, successful AI implementation requires certified professionals, which drives up education and development expenses. Information security also poses a critical challenge, given the growing threats of cyberattacks and data breaches. Ethical issues, including data privacy and the risk of discrimination, further underscore the need for careful consideration in AI deployment [4].

Application of AI in various business areas

Modern technological advances are increasingly driven by AI, which is becoming a key factor in innovation and development. In business, it automates processes, improves customer interaction and analyzes large volumes of data to support strategic decision-making. **In advertising and sales**, AI can analyze customer behavior, provide personalized offers and improve service quality. Predictive analytics algorithms help companies anticipate customer needs and adapt marketing strategies accordingly. In human resource management, AI optimizes recruitment and assessment processes by selecting candidates based on certain criteria, conducting initial resume screening, and even automating the talent selection process. This reduces recruitment costs and increases operational efficiency [5].

Supply chain management also benefits from the adoption of AI through logistics optimization, inventory control, and demand forecasting. AI-based software can analyze large volumes of supply chain data, reducing logistics costs and minimizing disruptions. **In finance**, AI plays an important role in assessing risk, analyzing data, and predicting market trends. Banks and investment firms are using AI to assess creditworthiness and risk, allowing them to make financial decisions faster and more accurately. In addition, AI-based accounting automation reduces labor costs and increases the accuracy of calculations. **In manufacturing**, AI supports high-quality production and lowers equipment maintenance costs. For instance, predictive analytics can forecast equipment failures, minimizing downtime and cutting repair expenses [6].

For successful AI integration in business processes, it is essential to follow theoretical integration models. A commonly used model is a phased implementation approach, involving key stages: diagnosing company needs, strategy development, pilot testing, and full integration. At each stage, it is crucial to consider the company's specifics, resources, and strategic goals to minimize risks and ensure AI is effectively adapted to organizational processes. For example, at **Amazon**, AI is actively used to optimize business processes and improve the quality of customer service. One of the most notable examples of the use of AI in

this field is the personalization algorithm, which operates on the basis of ML and big data analysis methods. The specified algorithm analyzes the behavioral patterns of users, their preferences and purchase history in order to offer goods and services that best meet the individual interests of each client. Using this approach allows Amazon not only to stimulate sales growth, but also to build long-term relationships with customers through an individualized approach. In addition, AI helps optimize logistics processes and inventory management by predicting the level of demand for products in various regions. This, in turn, leads to lower costs and faster delivery of goods, which increases the competitiveness of Amazon. Creating a convenient and high-quality service for customers, as well as obtaining significant strategic advantages for the company, are the result of using the described technologies.

The risks associated with implementing AI

There are significant risks associated with AI adoption that must be managed to ensure safe and effective technology use. One of the primary risks is **job displacement**, as process automation reduces the need for certain roles, potentially causing social tension. Additionally, the **high cost of AI technology** can pose a constraint for small and medium-sized enterprises. Other limitations relate to ensuring **legal and ethical compliance**. For example, processing large amounts of data necessitates strict information security standards, which may be challenging to meet, given the high requirements for data privacy and security. **Ethical considerations**, especially regarding discrimination in areas such as hiring or financial decision-making, are also increasingly critical [7].

Security risks are intensifying as advancements in AI technologies progress, including heightened threats of misuse and cyberattacks. The rapid development and concentration of AI capabilities within a limited number of organizations and nations could further exacerbate socioeconomic inequalities, restricting the diversity and accessibility of AI applications across sectors. Moreover, excessive dependence on AI systems may diminish human creativity and critical thinking skills, as automated solutions replace traditional problem-solving approaches.

Additionally, AI-driven misinformation and manipulation pose significant threats to public trust, as fabricated content generated by advanced algorithms can mislead and misinform individuals on a mass scale [8]. These risks contribute to a broader erosion of trust in information systems, impacting societal cohesion and governance. The unintended consequences of AI, stemming from both design oversights and emergent behaviors, have the potential to disrupt social and economic structures, often with adverse effects on people and communities. Furthermore, the development of AI raises critical ethical concerns, particularly regarding the technology's alignment with human values and societal norms. As AI systems become more autonomous and integrated into daily life, ensuring that they operate in ways that are transparent, equitable, and consistent with human rights is essential to their responsible use and acceptance within society.

Conclusion

The introduction of AI technologies into business processes provides companies with significant opportunities to increase efficiency, reduce costs and strengthen competitive advantages. The theoretical analysis has shown that the use of AI can optimize key areas of activity, including marketing, supply chain management, recruitment and personnel management, as well as financial and production processes. AI technologies allow you to automate routine operations and enhance the analytical function, which contributes to more accurate decision-making and increased overall productivity.

However, the use of AI comes with certain challenges and limitations. These include the high cost of implementation, the need for qualified specialists, as well as significant risks associated with data protection and ethical aspects. These factors point to the need for a balanced and step-by-step approach to integrating AI into the business environment. Thus, for the successful and safe implementation of AI, companies need to take into account both its advantages and potential risks, as well as develop strategies aimed at minimizing negative consequences and maximizing the effectiveness of technology use.

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